

Enforcement of Power of Sale in Secured Credit Transactions in Nigeria: Matters Arising

Busari Morufu Salawu, PhD.

*Department of Public and International Law,
Faculty of Law, Osun State University, Osogbo, Nigeria.*

Email: busari.salawu@uniosun.edu.ng

ORCID ID: 0009-0003-9379-1939

Abstract:

Mortgage defaults make the business of lending very difficult in Nigeria and retard access to capital for sustainable shelter, industrial and commercial developments. Though remedies such as specific performance, judicial foreclosure and appointment of the receiver exist to enforce the mortgage, the process of achieving them through court litigation has made such options unalluring. The paper focuses on the mortgagee's power of sale, which is a non-judicial remedy, examines conditions precedent for its use and appraises challenges to its enforcement in mortgages with land securities. A doctrinal method relying on primary (statutes and case law) and secondary source (textbooks, journal articles, reports and conference proceedings) is used to analyse the data collected. While most statutes on the Mortgagees Power of Sale (MPOS) in Nigeria emanate from its colonial heritage of common law with pockets of reforms. Conflicting land rights based on multiple land tenures, complex land registrations and consents requirements, non-digitised land registry and corruption make the enforcement of the right difficult. Obsolete laws and conflicting regulations are proposed for amendment, while asphyxiating corruption should be tackled by political will and social reorientation.

Keywords: Governor's Consent, Judicial Foreclosure, Legal Charge, Legal Due Date, Legal Mortgage, Power of Sale.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Mortgage industry in Nigeria is confronted with challenges relating to its enforcement of the covenant to repay the loans and the interests. Many lending institutions have collapsed due to this menace.¹ According to Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC), between 1998 and 2018, 53 deposit money banks were closed following the revocation of their operating licenses, while 103 microfinance banks were closed the same period. Since 2018 and now, up to 15 additional deposit and microfinance banks had been distressed.² The data from the analysis of 3,197 defaulted mortgages between 1991 and 2011 in Nigeria reveals that various factors such as borrower status, borrowers' history of default, year of borrowing, business relationship with the bank, loan supervision, age of collateral and location of the real estate collaterals positively affected loan defaults are positive determinants of loan recovery, while the inflation growth rate, interest growth rates, priority of collaterals, and collateral revaluation are significant but inversely to loan recovery,³ while factors such as loan-to-value, loan size and loan duration, though insignificant, have positive influence on likelihood of loan recovery.⁴ While focusing on Nigerian property statutes and practice, this paper will make some comparison to mortgage laws and practice in Ghana, to reflect common legal heritage from England.

1.1 Problem of the study

Many studies have been conducted on mortgage laws in Nigeria, but few have investigated problems encountered by lending houses in enforcing mortgages through mortgage powers of sale.⁵ Focusing on these will assist banks to recover nonperforming loans guaranteed by the security of land. It will further generate literature to fill the gap in existing literature and improve policy making in law. Based on the above, the study formulates the following broad aim, namely, the consideration of challenges in the mortgagee's power of sale which is a non-judicial remedy. The objectives of the paper are to:

1. give an overview of the mortgagee's power of sale,

¹ NDIC, 'Closed Financial Institutions' ndic.gov.ng/failure-resolution/closed-financial-institutions/ > accessed 5 December 2024.

² *ibid.*

³ M. O. Bello, A.O. Adewusi, T.B Oyedokun, T.A Ashaolu & N.B Ezeokoli, 'Analysis of Recovery Determinants of Defaulted Mortgages in Nigerian Lending Industry' *European Journal of Business and Management* (2013) (5)(21)50.

⁴ *ibid.*

⁵ Deji Olanrewaju and Seun Oke, 'An Appraisal of Mortgage Security for Bank Lending in Nigeria' *Zenith Economic Quarterly* (2011) (7)(4) < <https://share.google/cYqfn7T6OrqCjsQOt> > accessed 12 November 2025; Solomon O. Afolabi, 'A Critical Examination of the Application of the Neighbourhood Principle to Mortgage's Duty to Third Parties in Common Law Legal Systems' *International Journal of Law, Justice and Jurisprudence* (2022) (2)(2), 1-4 < <https://share.google/IIa7BIc9UZg6tT6wq> > accessed 12 November 2025; Busari Morufu Salawu, 'An Examination of the Legal Framework for Parties Rights when Mortgaging under Nigerian Property Legislation' *Turf Law*, (2025) (5) (1),1-18 < <https://share.google/1MKjwMhORyZOxucFd> > accessed 12 November 2025.

2. examine conditions precedent for using the power and,
3. appraise challenges to the enforcement in mortgages with land securities.

1.2 Methodology

A doctrinal method relying on primary (statutes and case law) and secondary source (textbooks, journal articles, reports and conference proceedings) is used to analyse the data collected. The primary source relies on the analysis of statutes such as the Land Use Act, 1978;⁶ Conveyancing Act 1881;⁷ Property Conveyancing Law, 1959;⁸ Mortgages and Property Law, 2012,⁹ etc., and the case law. The secondary source dwells on the analysis of materials from textbooks, journal articles and the internet.

1.3 Structure of the study

The paper is structured in six parts. Part one contains preliminaries such as the background, problem of the study and objectives while part two is literature review. Part three is the overview of the mortgagee's power of sale and part four examines conditions precedents for the use of the remedy. Part five appraises challenges to enforcement of the remedy while part six is the conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Existing literature on the creation and enforcement of mortgages is reviewed in this section. The study conducted by Afolabi examined the nature of the duty of care in exercising the power of sale in mortgages. It was found, among others, that the neighbourhood principle was applicable to the lender who is embarking on the sale of mortgage property upon default, especially with respect to the mortgagor and other third-party interests. Salawu examines the legal framework of parties' rights in the mortgage of land,¹⁰ and the modes of creating legal mortgages,¹¹ under the Nigerian law. Wigwe aptly discussed practice and the law of possession where the author interrogated the use of land as security for loans under the Land Use Act, 1978.¹² These studies do not focus on the jurisprudence of the power of sale, conditions precedents for using the power and the challenges to enforcement in mortgage securities.

Furthermore, Enakireru appraises the right of ownership, the equitable right of redemption, rules of governing the right of redemption, suspension of the right to redeem covenant imposing penalty and collateral advantage of statutory power of sale and

⁶ Cap L5, Law of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004.

⁷ Law of England.

⁸ Cap 100, Law of Western Region of Nigeria, 1959.

⁹ (As Amended), Law of Lagos State.

¹⁰ Salawu, 'An Examination of the Legal Framework for Parties Rights when Mortgaging under Nigerian Property Legislation.'

¹¹ Busari Morufu Salawu, 'Creation of Mortgages in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges' *ABUAD Law Journal* (2025) (13) (1) < <https://share.google/bszavSWKllYnrWA3F> > accessed 12 November 2025.

¹² Chris Wigwe, *Mortgage Practice and the Law of Possession in Nigeria* (Readwide Publishers, 2012).

protection of innocent purchasers, application of sale proceeds, etc.¹³ The focus of the study was too broad for any meaningful legal analysis, particularly on the mortgagee's power of sale as conceived in this study.

Aina and Adeosun examined the challenges of utilizing mortgages for bank loans such as title issues under the Land Use Act, 1978, multiple laws relating to mortgages and land, cumbersome process of land registration and insufficient collateral. The authors suggested the reform of Land Use Act, 1978 and the repeal of multiple laws on mortgage to ease mortgage transactions in Nigeria.¹⁴ In the same vein, Ihekwoaba conducted an analysis of mortgage transactions in Nigeria.¹⁵ While these contribute to the understanding of the law of mortgages in Nigeria, they lack the in-depth analysis of the principles and practice of enforcing the remedy of power of sale by the mortgagees. Hence, the need for this study.

3. OVERVIEW OF MORTGAGEE'S POWER OF SALE

3.1 Mortgage market penetration in Nigeria

The importance of shelter to the global human community cannot be overemphasized. It is the mankind's cardinal need, aside from food, and this has been recognized by Abraham Maslow when he categorized it as a basic order need, the satiation of which is mandatory before the achievement of higher other needs.¹⁶ The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 11 captures it as a first target in its targets for "Sustainable Cities and Communities".¹⁷

The United Nations International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESR) to which Nigeria is a signatory recognizes right to adequate standard of living for self and the family when it states in its Article 7 that:

The States Parties to the present Covenant recognize the right of everyone to the enjoyment of just and favourable conditions of work which ensure, in particular:

(a) Remuneration which provides all workers, as a minimum, with:

¹³ EO Enakireru, 'Appraisal of the right of the Mortgagor vis-à-vis the Impact of the Legal Instruments under the Nigerian Legal System' *Journal of Law and Human Rights* (2022) (6)(1). 106-144.

¹⁴ Kunle Aina and Funmi Adeogun, 'Mortgage as Security for Loan in Nigeria' *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization* (2025) (149), 39-50 < <https://share.google/Mj8voYWcZTq14AwaY> > accessed 13 November 2025.

¹⁵ Udechukwu Goodluck Ihekwoaba, 'A Holistic Analysis of Mortgage Transactions in Nigeria' *Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka Journal of Private Property Law* (2024)(1)(2), 102-112.

¹⁶ Mary West, 'Maslow Hierarchy of Needs: Uses and Criticisms' (*Medical News Today*, 20 June 2025) < <https://share.google/oY7ZtjNaEIU1fGjLe> > accessed 13 November 2025.

¹⁷ UN-Habitat, 'Cities and Communities in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable' (United Nations) < <https://share.google/uoOOCsLVLVhpM1py> > accessed 13 November 2025.

- (ii) A decent living for themselves and their families in accordance with the provisions of the present Covenant.

This provision has been captured in the Nigerian Constitution as a right to shelter. It states that:¹⁸

- (2) The State shall direct its policy towards ensuring-
 - (d) that suitable and adequate shelter, right to food and food security, reasonable national minimum living wage, old age care and pensions, and unemployment, sick benefits and welfare of the disabled are provided for all citizens.

Although non-justiciable,¹⁹ the provision of this right is an indication of the value placed on the provision of adequate shelter and improved standard of living in Nigeria.

However, the housing situation in Nigeria has not reflected this robust legal framework. The World Bank Survey indicated that with current trends in urbanisation, Nigeria needs at least 700,000 housing units across different segments annually, while only 100,000 units are produced, resulting in accumulated deficits of 17 million units.²⁰ A 2024 World Bank Report indicated that 49% of Nigeria's population lived in slums in 2020, while a housing deficit of 17 million indicated in its 2013 Report had increased to 25 million units in 2022.²¹

Based on these gory reports, the Central Bank of Nigeria assessed the legal framework for mortgage financing in Nigeria and has come up with the findings that the multiple, and rather conflicting legal framework should be streamlined, and a uniform Model Mortgages and Foreclosure Law it proposed should be passed into law by various states. It was believed that this would reduce substantially the incidence of non-performing loans placed at 4.4%.²² According to the Ministry of Housing and Urban Development as at 2023, and more than six years after the model law has been proposed, only four out of the 36 states have passed it.²³

¹⁸ Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (CFRN) (As amended), Cap C23, LFN 2004, s. 16.2.

¹⁹ *ibid*, s.6(6)(c).

²⁰ World Bank, *Nigeria: Developing Housing Finance* (World Bank, 2013) < <https://share.google/YCBrwIO6uoqHLg2mB> > accessed 14 November 2025.

²¹ World Bank, *Nigeria Development Update* (World Bank, 2025) < <https://share.google/J4F8hLv3boUKfsoPW> > accessed 14 November 2025.

²² Victor Gbonegun, 'Housing: How Non-Adoption of Foreclosure Law Stifles Mortgage Investment?' (Lagos: *Guardian*, 8 January 2025) < <https://share.google/UcT01pyZGvrfRlv4w> > accessed 13 November 2025.

²³ Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development, 'Keynote Address by the Honourable Minister of Housing and Urban Development at the 20th Edition of Mortgage Banking Sub-Sector CEOs Annual Retreat at the Transcorp Hilton, Abuja on 2 December 2023' < <https://share.google/vDJtPticVRVbpEomc> > accessed 13 November 2025.

Factors responsible for low penetration of mortgages in Nigeria are multiple.²⁴ On the part of financial institutions, these include maturity mismatch, limited capacity by primary mortgage banks to grant long term loans, high interest rates, onerous enforcement procedures and fallouts from legislative clumsiness of the Land Use Act, 1978.²⁵ On the part of the mortgagors, the factors include exorbitant registration costs,, high rate of unregistered titles arising from the uncertainty of titles under the Land Use Act, the challenge of “double perfection” of mortgages, low mortgage literacy and reducing disposable income for mortgage financing.²⁶

The increasing efforts of the Mortgage Refinance Company PLC, which had invested up to 18 billion naira in the industry in the last decade has ameliorated some of these factor by making home ownership affordable, accessible and stable.²⁷ Although the Model Mortgages and Foreclosures Law it proposed for adoption by states for uniform transaction has not been adopted by majority of states, it is hoped that as more states adopt it, the problem of obsolete, and contradictory legal framework in the industry will be resolved.

3.2 Evolutionary trend

The power of sale (PoS) is a non-judicial sale which operates when the mortgage deed does not contain any contrary intention. The exclusion of power of sale from the mortgage deed makes it possible for the mortgagee to enforce through this method as a part of their freedom of contract. Hence, parties may delete, vary or extend it as they deem fit.²⁸ Its omission does not derogate from its use because if the mortgage deed is silent on it, the statute governing mortgage relations in the jurisdiction the deed was made would come into operation to govern the relationship.

3.2.1 Common law PoS

The power of sale originated as a common law remedy for realising mortgages. Initially, the lender did not possess power of sale because borrowers retained the right of redemption.²⁹

Over time, parties to mortgages developed the use of contractual clauses which conferred on the lender the right of sale without having any recourse to the court. This power could be endowed on the lender by the mortgagor through an agreement in the mortgage.

²⁴ Kehinde Ogundimu, ‘Legal and Regulatory Framework for the mortgage Industry in Nigeria’ *Economic Financial Review* (Central Bank, December 2019), 85-94 < <https://share.google/XxPxRyLxBbnzEols1>> accessed 13 November 2025.

²⁵ *ibid.*

²⁶ *ibid.*

²⁷ *ibid.*

²⁸ Section 123 (3) PCL 1959; Section 19 (3) CA 1881; Section 35 (3) MPL 2015.

²⁹ K. Gray, *Elements of Land Law* (London, Butterworth, 1987) 614

3.2.2 Statutory efforts

The MPoS which commenced at common law was later canonized in the passage of the Trustees and Mortgagees Act 1860.³⁰ The Act was later repealed and replaced by the Conveyancing Act (CA) 1881.³¹ Although the 1860 Act was applicable to Ghana which received English Law through the Supreme Court Ordinance of 1876, it did not apply to Nigeria because English law became applicable in Nigeria on 1 January 1900 through the Interpretation Act.³² The purpose of the Trustees and Mortgages Act as a precursor to other statutory provisions is enormous. Its section 15(1) which survived as section 19(1) of the Conveyancing Act states that:

A mortgagee, where the mortgage is made by deed, shall, by virtue of this Act, have the following powers, to the like extent as if they had been in terms conferred by the mortgage deed but not further (namely):

- (i) A power when the mortgage money has become due, to sell, or to concur with any other person in selling, the mortgaged property, or any part thereof, either subject to prior charges, or not, and either together or in lots, by public auction or by private contract, subject to such conditions respecting title, or evidence of title, or other matter, as he (the mortgagee) thinks fit, with power to vary any contract for sale, and to buy in at an auction, or to rescind any contract for sale, and to re-sell, without being answerable for any loss occasioned thereby...

This section forms the basis of the mortgagee's various statutes regulating mortgage practice in Nigeria.³³ Power of sale is implied in every mortgage made by deed (both legal and equitable),³⁴ and a legal charge.³⁵ The implication of MPoS is that a mortgage may be enforced upon default, if conditions stipulated in the mortgage instrument or implied by the statutes have been met.³⁶ The common law MPoS is inherited by the former British colonies in Sub Saharan Africa. It survives up till now with some modifications in the region. For example, Section 20 of the Home Mortgage Finance Act makes provision for the disposition of mortgaged property upon default.³⁷

3.2.3 Judicial sale

The judicial sale is initiated by the lender who institutes the court proceeding upon the default of the mortgagor.³⁸ Apart from equitable mortgages, sale of securities in legal

³⁰ S. 15 of the Act

³¹ S. 19(1) CA 1881

³² Cap 123, Law of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN), 2004, s. 19(2).

³³ CA 1881, Section 19 (1); PCL 1959, Section 123(1) and MPL 2012, Section 35(1).

³⁴ PCL, Section 123 (1).

³⁵ CA, Section 19(1); PCL, Section 123 (1); MPL 2012; Section 35 (1).

³⁶ I.O. Smith, *Law of Secured Credit* (Lagos, Ecovatch Publication 2001)78.

³⁷ 2008 (Act 770). Law of Ghana.

³⁸ Tokunboh Orimobi, 'Looking at a Mortgagee's Power Of Sale And Court Ordered Sale in Lagos State' *Businessday*, (October 22, 2015) accessed from <www.businessday.ng> April, 2023

mortgages can also be enforced by judicial sale.³⁹ Hence, all equitable mortgages in Lagos State of Nigeria, including those by the deposit of deeds or charge would have to either apply to courts to order the mortgagor to execute a legal mortgage,⁴⁰ or to a court for a judicial sale.⁴¹ The implication of the provision is that an equitable mortgage created by depositing of title deeds or a charge accompanied by an assignment without more in form of an accompanying memo, can only exercise the PoS through the court.

A judicial sale offers the mortgagor opportunity to be heard before the mortgage security is sold. It also affords the equitable creditor an opportunity to dispose of the security in case of default, rather than waiting for an elusive opportunity of specific performance or a declaratory right of entry from the courts. Despite the above advantages, judicial sale is still unalluring because it exposes rights of lenders to the tortuous court process.

4. CONDITIONS PRECEDENT FOR MORTGAGEE'S POWER OF SALE (MPoS)

4.1 When power of sale arises

The content of a mortgage deed governs the contractual relationships as courts in Nigeria have adopted this international best practice unless when doing so will lead to manifest injustice.⁴² Parties reserve the right to either adopt, adapt, vary or totally exclude the MPoS clauses in the statutes.

The pertinent issue is when does the power of sale arise? An examination of major enactments on mortgages in Nigeria reveals that: ⁴³ “the mortgage should be by deed”; the legal due date must have passed, and no agreement against sale must have been made before it could arise.⁴⁴ These conditions desire some critical look to understand the principles and determine their importance in the exercise of MPoS.

4.2 Mortgage by deed

The power arises in a mortgage by deed or a legal charge by deed. ⁴⁵ In *London and County Banking Company v Goddard*,⁴⁶ an equitable lender was held to be capable of enforcing the mortgage through MPoS, although other equitable mortgages not by deed could not do so under section 19 of CA 1881. Rather, an equitable mortgage not by deed requires an order of a judicial sale for an effective transfer of the security through PoS.

³⁹Mortgages and Property Law (MPL), Law of Lagos State 2012 (as amended), s 21(1).

⁴⁰ *Ibid* s 18.

⁴¹ *Ibid*, s 21(1).

⁴²*Okonkwo v CCB (Nig Ltd)*, (2003) 8 NWLR (Pt. 822) 347

⁴³ 1881, Law of England applicable in some parts of Nigeria, Property Conveyancing Law (PCL), Cap 100, Law of Western Nigeria; Mortgages and Property Law 2012 (as amended) Law of Lagos State Nigeria Mortgages and Foreclosure Law, 2020 Law of Ekiti State, Nigeria.

⁴⁴ S. 19 (1) Conveyancing Act; S. 123 Property Conveyancing Law and S. 35 (1) Mortgages and Property Law.

⁴⁵ *ibid*.

⁴⁶ (1897) 1 CH.642.

From the express provisions of sections 18 and 21 and the wording of section 35 of Mortgage and Property Law 2012,⁴⁷ it appears that equitable mortgages created by mere deposit of title deeds accompanied by memorandum can no longer access statutory power of sale. Section 18 states that:

- (1) As from the commencement of this Law, an equitable mortgage of a right to occupancy shall not be created by a mere deposit of title or charge on a property except it is accompanied by an agreement to create a legal mortgage in favour of the mortgagee or in the case of mortgage of an equitable interest in a property by an assignment of an equitable interest in favour of the mortgagee with a provision for ceaser on redemption.
- (2) Provided that in a case of mortgage by deposit of title or charge accompanied by an agreement to create a legal mortgage, a mortgagee may, within 30 days by an Originating Summons, bring an action in court requiring the mortgagor to execute a legal mortgage in his favour and thereafter exercise the powers of legal mortgagee under the law.

This section outlaws the use of a mere title deed accompanied by a memo to create an equitable deed in compliance with section 21 and 22, Land Use Act, which requires formal consent or approvals for the transfer of titles in legal mortgages and the prohibition of any form of transfer of land titles without such approvals. Transfer of mere title deeds do not fulfil this cardinal provision. This is a departure from the positions under section 19 (1) CA and section 123 PCL where remedial devices could be used to conduct the transfer of the security from the mortgagor to the third party.

4.3 Expiration of the legal due date

The legal due date for the realisation of the mortgage is based on the provision of the contract agreement. This means that the due date may be when the total payment is payable or when the installment payment is in default. The MPoS will only be due when the date for the repayment has passed or a breach of a covenant has occurred which necessitates a recall of the principal and the interest.⁴⁸ The mortgage agreement may contain a clause which provides for the return of the outstanding sum and the interest, wholly or by instalment upon the mortgagor's default.⁴⁹ It may also provide for

⁴⁷ (As Amended). Law of Lagos.

⁴⁸ E. Chianu, *Law of Securities for Bank Advances* (Mortgage of Land) (3rd edition, Ambik Press, Benin City, 2017) 333.

⁴⁹ *SON Okafor & Sons v Nigerian Housing Devt Society Ltd* (1972) 7 NSCC 271; *Nigerian Housing Development*

acceleration clause on the default of an instalment which makes the entire balance immediately due.⁵⁰

The question that becomes pertinent is that in an agreement to pay by instalments, at which point will the power of sale arise? The PoS will arise when there is a default in the payment of any instalment.⁵¹ It was held in *Payne v Cardiff Rural District Council*⁵² that the power would be enforceable when a mortgagor fails to pay an instalment. The payment of all outstanding arrears after an initial default could not stop the sale, unless the mortgagor repays all the outstanding sum and the interest to the court.⁵³

In Nigeria, the moment the legal due date is passed, or the mortgagor has breached the covenant to pay the interest and payment promptly,⁵⁴ the power of sale has arisen.

In *SON Okafor & Sons Ltd v Nigerian Housing Development Society Ltd*,⁵⁵ the loan was granted in instalments to enable the mortgagor to build a house. The payment would commence immediately after the loan was granted. At the time of the dispute, £330 remained unpaid to the mortgagor whereas the mortgagor owed several instalments on interests. When the property was advertised for sale, the mortgagor applied to the court to stop the sale on account that the power of sale had not arisen because the loan had not been fully granted. The request failed because the contract empowered the creditor to sell the security upon default in payment of instalments. It was held that the exercise of power was independent of whether the entire loan had been granted or not. Also, *UBN v Fajebe Foods Ltd*,⁵⁶ which had similar facts to *Okafor's* case, the Supreme Court towed the same line.

Based on the foregoing decisions, the basic rule for installment payment is that the payment should not be allowed to be in arrears. The moment the payment falls into arrears, all outstanding sums and arrears would have to be paid to forestall the enforcement by MPoS.⁵⁷

4.4 No contrary intention to exercise power of sale

The PoS arises when no contrary agreement is expressed in the contractual deed. The parties can expressly exclude the statutory power of sale in the mortgage deed as it cannot

Society Ltd v Mumuni & Or(1977) NSCC 65, *Union Bank of Nigeria Ltd v Fajebe Foods Ltd* (1998) 6 NWLR (Pt.

554) 380.

⁵⁰ E Chianu, *Law of Securities for Bank Advance (Mortgage of Land)*, 334.

⁵¹ See *Payne v Cardiff Rural District Council* (1932) IKB 241; *Nigerian Housing Development Society Ltd v Mumuni & Or* (1977) NSCC 65, among others.

⁵² *ibid.*

⁵³ *ibid.*

⁵⁴ E Chianu, *Law of Securities for Bank Advances (Mortgage of Land)* (Third Edition, Ambik Press, 2017), 333.

⁵⁵ *Supra* (1974) 7 NSCC 271.

⁵⁶ (1998) 6 NWLR (Pt. 554) 380.

⁵⁷ Per Justice Udoma JSC in *Nigerian Housing Development Society Ltd v Mumuni & Or.* (1977) NSCC 65

be implied.⁵⁸ However, if a mortgage deed is silent on the power of sale, it may be implied since regulatory statutes in Nigeria,⁵⁹ contain a provision for the MPoS, if such is not specifically excluded. Section 123(1) PCL specifically provides *inter alia* that: “--- subject to such conditions respecting title, or other matter, as the mortgagee thinks fit with power to vary any contract for sale, and to resell, without being answerable for any loss occasioned thereby---.”

The implication of the above is that any contrary intention may vary this statutory provision. But for such contrary intention to be valid, it must be expressly included in the mortgage deed, and no oral proof of the contrary intention shall be tenable before the court.⁶⁰

The question that may arise is that in the absence of any contrary intention in the mortgage deeds, can the MPoS be varied by means of a waiver from the mortgagee later, especially in the face of default? A waiver is a voluntary or intentional act to forgo a known right or dispense with the performance of a thing that one is entitled to.⁶¹ For a waiver to be valid, it must not be a unilateral notification by a party to another, not supported by an agreement.⁶² The implication of this is that the waiver must be mutual and the decision consensual for it to convey the desired benefit, or prevent the impending forbearance.

This came up in *Nigeria Advertising Services Ltd v UBA*,⁶³ when the notice of the intention to sell the security was served and the mortgagor requested for a waiver of four weeks. The mortgagee did not respond to the request but proceeded to embark on the sale. Upon the sale, an application was moved by the mortgagor for the reversal on the grounds that a bank draft was deposited to the mortgagee to redeem the property few weeks after its sale. The court turned down the request and affirmed the sale because no representation was given to the mortgagor that might amount to a waiver. Also, *Okonkwo v CCB (Nigeria) Plc and 2 Ors*,⁶⁴ the plaintiff (mortgagor) and an appellant at the Supreme Court, had mortgaged his building at No 133 Aba-Owerri. Road Aba, as security for a loan of #60,000= repayable in one year. When the mortgagor defaulted for over six years, relevant notices were sent to him without response. The defendants/respondents initially wanted to sell the house in 1982. But the action was stopped by the payment of #21,000=. The building was later advertised and sold on a notice of three days on 1 February 1988. The claim that the sum of #96,000= was raised for the payment of the loan was rejected. One of the issues in contention was that a waiver was made. In affirming the sale, the Supreme Court noted that:

It was common ground that the relationship between
the plaintiff and the first defendant is contractual and

⁵⁸ See s. 123 (1) PCL, s. 19(1) CA and s. 35 MPL.

⁵⁹ F.J. Oniekoro, *Mortgages in Nigeria: Law and Practice* (Chenglo Ltd. Enugu, 2007) 179.

⁶⁰ *Missri v Bank of West Africa* (1967) Nig. Commercial LR 427; *Oyefeso v UCH Board of Management* (1980) Nig. Commercial LR 94.

⁶¹ E. Chianu, *Law of Securities for Bank Advanced* (Mortgage of Land) (3rd edition, Ambic Press, Benin City, 2017) 346.

⁶² *Ibid.*

⁶³ (1999) 8 NWLR (pt. 616) 546.

⁶⁴ *Okonkwo v CCB (Nig) Ltd* (2003) All NLR (Pt 1) 464- 465.

governed by Exhibit 'B', the Deed of Legal Mortgage. This being so, extrinsic evidence will generally not be accepted to vary the terms agreed upon.⁶⁵

The sale was affirmed because the mortgagor's right to be given notice under section 20 of the CA 1881 was waived, thereby excluding the statutory provisions in that regard. It was resolved that by his waiver, the provision of the Auctioneer Laws requiring notice was also set aside.⁶⁶ However, in his dissenting judgement, Tobi JSC noted that in the instant case,⁶⁷ the defence of a waiver could be said to be available to the mortgagor if it was pleaded, but at the same time it could not replace the need to give notice to the public if it is so required by the public policy. The eminent jurist argues:

By clause 8 of Exhibit 'B', appellant can only waive his right to the statutory notice under the Auctioneers' Law of Former Eastern Nigeria, 1963. He cannot waive the right to notice members of the public or third parties who will be interested in the auction sale. After all, it is good law that a party cannot waive the legal right of members of the public because the right does not belong to him. One cannot waive a right that belongs to some other person or persons.

The purport of the dissenting judgement was that (i) the Court of Appeal erred in law by raising the issue of waiver *suo motu*, (ii) assuming the waiver was pleaded, it was not possible for a party to waive the right that belonged to members of the public under the Auctioneers Law which provided that the public should be given the seven day notice before proceeding on the sale and (iii) for failure to comply with section 9 of the Auctioneers' Law, the sale was null and void.

The position held by the learned justice in the dissenting judgement would have done the justice of the case were it to be affirmed in the lead judgement. The lead decision appears to have overlooked the need to give notice to the public which could not be waived by either party and the issue of fraud which the hasty sale could have led to. Hence, the cardinal rule appears to be that those rights relating to the parties could be waived and not rights belonging to another person or the public.

4.5 Exercising power of sale of the mortgagee

This power arises after the due date, provided the mortgage is by deed and no contrary intention is indicated by the parties. However, the power of sale must be exerciseable

⁶⁵ Per Kutigi JSC, delivery the lead judgement.

⁶⁶ Cap 12 Laws of Eastern Region S. 19

⁶⁷ Ibid

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which in other words means that should be ripe for enforcement. Section 125 of the PCL provides for the situation when this is ripe:⁶⁸

A mortgagee shall not exercise the power of sale by this Law unless and until-

- (i) Notice requiring payment of the mortgage money has been served on the mortgagor or one or two or more mortgagors, and default has been made in payment of the mortgage money, or of part thereof, for three months after such service; or
- (ii) Some interest under the mortgage is in arrear and unpaid for two months after becoming due; or
- (iii) There has been a breach of some provision contained in the mortgage deed or in this Law, or in an enactment replaced by this Law, and on the part of the mortgagor, or of some person concurring in making the mortgage to be observed or performed, other than and beside as covenant for payment of the mortgage money or interest thereon.⁶⁹

From the statutory provisions, common to all statutes regulating mortgages, in Nigeria, three conditions set for the power of sale which has arisen to be exerciseable are discussed below:

4.5.1 Service of the demand notice

The notice demanding payment of mortgage sum must be served the mortgagor who must have defaulted for a minimum of three months after the service.⁷⁰ Under the MPL the period of notice is two months.⁷¹

The lender does not need to give information to the mortgagor that the property will be sold. What is required is the notice to demand for the payment of mortgage money which has fallen into arrears for three months.⁷² Section 125(i) clearly indicates that what is required is the notice requiring payment of the total sum and the period of notice is three months, which starts from the date it is served.⁷³

The service on the mortgagor is mandatory because there could be a third-party mortgage in which the borrower is different from the mortgagor.⁷⁴ It has been stated

⁶⁸ S. 125; MPL, S. 37.

⁶⁹ S. 37

⁷⁰ Section 20 CA; s. 125 (1) PCL.

⁷¹ Section 37(1)1.

⁷² Okonkwo v CCB.

⁷³ E. Chianu, *Law of securities for Bank Advances (Mortgage of Land)* (Third Edition, Ambik Press, Benin City, 2017) 356.

⁷⁴ O.E.M. Elujekor, "Avoiding the Pitfalls inherent in the Mortgages Power of Sale", March 1997, *Nigerian Law and Practice Journal*, 61-72.

orbiter that while parties may waive statutory provision(s) for themselves, such rights may not be waived for third parties or the public at large.⁷⁵ The Supreme Court minority decision in *Okonkwo v Co-operative Commerce Bank (Nigeria Plc) & Ors* is instructive on this.

When the mode of notice was stated, failure to comply with it would invalidate the sale.⁷⁶ In *Akinsola v Barclays Bank of Nigeria Ltd*,⁷⁷ the mortgagor was to repay the loan any time it was demanded in writing. The sale was invalidated by the court when the bank later sold the mortgaged property through an auctioneer without complying with the provision. It was held that the letter written by the Bank fell short of demand notice as stipulated by the agreement.

Another issue is the determination of the circumstances under which the demand for notice could be excluded by the parties. It has been contended that parties may exclude or vary the notice in the mortgage deed. Particularly, solicitors may, on behalf of mortgagees introduce clauses that may exclude or vary the requirement of notice because of the general view that such onerous conditions may be a disservice to mortgagees.⁷⁸ Clauses may be introduced in the deed to exclude the operation of section 125 (i) PCL or any other statutes⁷⁹ regulating the mortgage practice in any part of Nigeria. The right of others to notice may not be waivable.⁸⁰ Except for any express act of waiver exists, the notice given by a mortgagee upon mortgagor's default subsists until the power is exercised.⁸¹

Although the exclusion or waiver of notice may affect members of the public, on occasions where the exclusion could not lead to manifest injustice, it could be affirmed. But where injustice will result from it, or there is any evidence of fiduciary relationship between the parties, the 'no notice clause' would be unenforceable to avoid fraud. The above was the situation in *Cockburn v Edwards*,⁸² where the mortgagee was a solicitor, and the mortgagor was his client. It was held that the 'no notice clause' disentitling the mortgagor to notice before sale was improper. This position appears sound in view of the need to ensure that the mortgagor, who evidently is the weak party, is not unnecessarily railroad into entering unfair agreement.

4.5.2 Interest in arrears

Interest is the consideration that the lender receives from the mortgagor in return for the mortgage sum. MPoS will be exerciseable if an arrear of interest is not paid for a period

⁷⁵ Per Tobi JSC in *Okonkwo v Co-operation Commerce Bank (Nigeria Plc)*.

⁷⁶*Akinsola v Barclays Bank of Nigeria () C.C.H.J.* 48.

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*

⁷⁸ Emeka Chianu, *Law of Securities for Bank Advances (Mortgage of Land)*, (Third edition, Ambik Press, Benin City, 2017) 357.

⁷⁹ 111 S. 35(1) MPL 2012 .

⁸⁰*Okonkwo v Co-operative Bank Ltd.*

⁸¹ *Ojikutu v Agbonmagbe Bank Ltd & Ors* (1966) All N.L.R. 553.

⁸² (1881) 18 Ch D 449.

of two months which begins to run from the expiration of the legal due date and not before it.⁸³

Prior to its enforcement, a condition precedent under MPL is that a default in payment of arrears for two months requires a mandatory notice.⁸⁴ The subsection combines subsections (i) and (ii) of section 125 PCL in that the requirement of notice of default in payment and interest in arrears are lumped together in section 37(i) of the MPL, suggesting that notice of interest falling into arrears is essential under the enforcement through sale. But for the enforcement of this condition under CA and PCL, no notice is required.⁸⁵

The period of notice in sections 125(i) PCL and 20(i) CA for the payment of mortgage money, which is three months, has been reduced to two months by the MPL which is the same period for the payment of interest in arrears or instalment payment. Streamlining the requirement of notice for the payment of mortgage and interest arrears under MPL is a very good development because the mortgagee's actions on the security would be more transparent. This innovation appears to have been taken into consideration in the *obiter* of the apex court in *Babatunde v Bank of the North*⁸⁶ which emphasised that notice of sale was a condition to a valid sale. Despite the objections of commentators like Chianu, that such an *obiter* offends the best authorities and all statutes on the point,⁸⁷ the comment of the court in the case serves the purpose of justice.

4.5.3 Breach of the law or covenant in mortgage deed

A mortgage deed involves several covenants made by parties. Covenants are contained either in the mortgage deed or the law governing the transaction. A violation of any covenant makes the power of sale exercisable. Apart from the regular covenants for the repayment of the mortgage sum and regular payment of interest, other covenants may include: to insure, to repair the mortgaged property; not to sublet the mortgaged property without the consent of the mortgagee; to keep and observe other covenants in a lease agreement existing between the mortgagor and the head lessor.⁸⁸

When there is a breach of a provision, what are the likely actions that the mortgagee may take? First, the mortgagee may resolve to enforce the payment by exercising the power of sale or the foreclosure of the mortgaged property.⁸⁹ Or in the alternative, the mortgagee may give the mortgagor more time, despite the breach, in form of a waiver.⁹⁰ In such circumstances, the mortgagee would be estopped from renegeing on

⁸³ Section 18(1) CA; Section 125 (ii) PCL 1959 and Section 37 MPL; F.J. Oniekoro, 192

⁸⁴ MPL, S. 37(1)

⁸⁵ CA, Section 20(i); PCL, Section 125 (ii)

⁸⁶ (2011) 18 NWLR (Pt. 1279), 738, 778, per Adekeye JSC

⁸⁷ E. Chianu, *Law of Securities and Bank Advances (Mortgage of Land)*, 339.

⁸⁸ F.J. Oniekoro, *Mortgages in Nigeria: Law and Practice* 196.

⁸⁹ PCL, S. 123 (1).

⁹⁰ *Nigerian Advertising Services Ltd v United Bank for Africa* (1999) 8 NWLR (pt. 616) 546, (1912) 1 Ch. 789.

the representation and only the court that can decide whether the representation could be vacated.⁹¹

It is a trite law that for breach of any condition, the mortgagee is at liberty to enforce the right of sale. This is contingent upon due notice being given to the mortgagor and the payment of the loan falling in arrears in accordance with the statutes, or as regulated by the contracts.

5. CHALLENGES TO THE MPoS

5.1 Provisions of Land Use Act 1978 (LUA)

The compliance with the principles of the LUA such as the eminent domain of the Governor;⁹² the nature of right of occupancy;⁹³ definite duration of the term held by the grantee;⁹⁴ differences between the two rights of occupancy (Statutory Right of Occupancy and Customary Right of Occupancy);⁹⁵ nature of the deemed grant;⁹⁶ half hectare rule;⁹⁷ certificate of occupancy;⁹⁸ consent;⁹⁹ revocation¹⁰⁰ and compensation rules,¹⁰¹ must be complied with. These principles have introduced some complexities into the operation of the MPoS in Nigeria. Though introduced as an Act that would unify all land tenure practices in Nigeria, ease conveyancing practices and make land available for accelerated economic development, some of its provisions have engaged the attention of jurists as making conveyancing difficult.¹⁰²

The LUA governs the creation, the operation and the realisation of any conveyance in Nigeria, including mortgage. A legal mortgagee must be diligent in creating the mortgage, so that its enforcement remedies, especially, the power of sale, would not be caught up by non-compliance with the complex rules of the LUA.

Compliance with the above rules is mandatory for a successful enforcement of the power of sale. Perhaps, the most complex of these rules is the consent provision which has exhausted much judicial ink. Right from the seminal decision in *Savannah Bank v Ajilo*¹⁰³ to *Okuneye v FBN*¹⁰⁴ conflicting decisions were made that make alienation of land very difficult.

⁹¹ Ibid.

⁹² LUA, s.1.

⁹³ Ibid, s. 51(1).

⁹⁴ Ibid, s.8.

⁹⁵ See Ibid, Ss. 5 & 6

⁹⁶ See Ss. Ibid, Ss. 34 & 36.

⁹⁷ Ibid, S. 34 (5).

⁹⁸ Ibid, S. 9.

⁹⁹ Ibid, Ss. 21 & 22.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid, s. 28.

¹⁰¹ Ibid, S. 29.

¹⁰² Aina and Adeogun, 'Mortgage as Security for Loan in Nigeria' *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization* (2025)(149)39-50.

¹⁰³ (1989) 1 NWLR (Pt. 97) 305

¹⁰⁴ (1996) 6 NWLR (Pt. 457) 749

5.2 Multiple and obsolete regulatory framework

Multiple laws regulate the mortgage industry in Nigeria. These include Received English common law, statutes of general application in force in England as of 1st January 1900 and the doctrines of equity. These legal frameworks have since gone through several reviews in the originating jurisdiction. For instance, principles of common law and doctrines of equity continually gone through judicial scrutiny to determine their relevance, while Conveyancing Act 1881 has gone through several amendments, while it is the major regulatory law in Nigeria, with modifications by the subsequent domestic legislation like the Land Use Act 1978. While the Property Conveyancing Law 1959, Mortgages Property Law 2012 and Mortgages and Foreclosures Law 2020 are used in southwest Nigeria, Conveyancing Act regulates mortgages and property practice in other parts of the country. Efforts by the Nigerian Mortgage Refinance Company to make the states adopt uniform Model Mortgages and Foreclosure Law has not yielded positive results.

5.3 Duties of good faith

A lender owes the mortgagor the duties of good faith and care while exercising right of sale. The mortgagor is in a weak position in the mortgage transaction. The first obligation which a lender owes to the mortgagor is that of good faith at all stages in the exercise of PoS. This means that there must not be fraud, unfair dealing gross underrating or collusion at the sale.¹⁰⁵ The lack of good faith would vitiate the whole process. To stop the sale for the lack of good faith, evidence of bad faith and sale at undervalue or a collusion on the part of the defendants must be proved.¹⁰⁶ Hence, for a sale to be declared invalid, there must be evidence of fraud or gross undervalue in the sale of security. In view of the complex rules guiding the disposition of land, the duty of good faith is difficult to be discharged by lending houses.

5.4 Duty of care

Unlike other common law jurisdictions, the duty of care in the sale of mortgaged land has not received the attention of Nigerian courts.¹⁰⁷ This appears to be a major setback for mortgage practice in Nigeria. Sometimes, a lender may act *bona fide*, devoid of fraud or unfair dealing, yet the sale may be at a loss or at a gross undervalue.¹⁰⁸ In situations like this, what happens to the lender? Negligence in the observance of duty of care makes the lender liable for the loss. In Britain,¹⁰⁹ the mortgagee is responsible for the consequences of its negligence. The decision *Medforth v Blake* is not, however, applicable to Nigeria because the decision is not a part of the received law. Following the innovations introduced by MFL 2020,¹¹⁰ the situation is changing. This is as follows:

¹⁰⁵ I.O. Smith, *Practical Approach to Law of Real Property in Nigeria* (Revised edition, Lagos, Ecowatch Publications (Nigeria) Limited, 2013) 401

¹⁰⁶ See *ACB v Ihekwoaba*(1998) 10 NWLR (Pt. 571) 590 and *Ekah-Eteh v Nig Development Society Ltd & Anor* (1973) NSCC vol. 8, 373

¹⁰⁷ I.O. Smith, *Practical Approach to Law of Real Property in Nigeria*, op. cit. 403

¹⁰⁸ Afolabi, 'A Critical Examination of the Application of the Neighbourhood Principle to Mortgage's Duty to Third Parties in Common Law Legal Systems'

¹⁰⁹*Medforth v Blake* (1993) 3 All ER 104, for the common law position

¹¹⁰ See MFL S. 73(1)

Where a mortgagor is in default of a repayment obligation under a mortgage and remains on default at the expiry of the time provided for the rectification of the default in the notice served on him under section 63(1), a mortgagee may exercise its power to sell the mortgaged property. Provided that the mortgagee, its agents, contractors, employees or representatives must at all times exercise a duty of care in enforcing such power of sale is made at the prevailing market price and in accordance with this law.

Despite the foregoing, the precedent of the Supreme Court in *Eka-Etet v Nigerian Development Society Ltd, Anor*¹¹¹ which is a *locus classicus* in this area, appears to have suggested the need to take adequate precaution, not to be negligent or careless in conducting sale but it fails to set the duty of care as a requirement of the law. It was held that an obligation to sell at the best price is not part of the Nigerian law, what is applicable is merely to sell without fraud. A more recent approach that will incorporate the latest viewpoint canvassed in *Medforth's* case by the Nigerian courts is advocated.

The above position is yet to be incorporated into most the Nigerian statutes. Courts have been insisting on taking reasonable precaution in the observance of good faith in obtaining adequate market value, a proper price¹¹² and this need not be the best price.¹¹³ In *Pinnock v G.B. Ollivant & Co Ltd*,¹¹⁴ the plaintiff mortgaged his landed property to the defendant who sold it for £40 only which was admitted to be below the estimated market value of £100. The court held the sale was an 'utterly discretable transaction.'¹¹⁵ The court, therefore, awarded damages at the market value the property ought to have been sold, less the amount actually owing at the time of sale.

The implications of the above obligations are: (a) the sale should be carried out in good faith; (b) the court would not inquire as to the mortgagee's motive for carrying out the sale as such is immaterial;¹¹⁶ (c) the court would interfere into the sale if the price is so low to the extent that it occasions fraud;¹¹⁷ (d) that the duty of care which is protected under the Building Societies Act 1939, Section 10 in England is not yet protected under most Nigerian extant statutes on mortgage.¹¹⁸ It may, therefore, be submitted that the mortgagor is at the mercy of the mortgagee in this regard because the only obligation the

¹¹¹ (1973) NSCC 2018, 373

¹¹² *Maina v United Bank of Nigeria Ltd* (1985) HNCLR 828; *Eka-Etet v Nigeria Housing Development (NHDS) & Anor* (1973) 6 SC 183

¹¹³ *Eka-Etet v NHDS* supra

¹¹⁴ (1934) LJR - WACA

¹¹⁵ *Ibid* 167 per Graham Paul, J.

¹¹⁶ *Nash v Eads* (1880) 25 SOL. Jo.95

¹¹⁷ *Warner v Jacob* (1882) 20 Ch.D 220 at 224

¹¹⁸ See S. 73(2) Mortgages and Foreclosure Law (MFL) 2020, No 17 of Ekiti State

mortgagee owes the mortgagor is that of good faith. The moment the duty is fulfilled, even when the sale is at an undervalue, the sale is not in any way vitiated. Furthermore, in situations where fraud is evident, Nigerian courts have usually been awarding damages rather than outright invalidation of the whole process.¹¹⁹ This, perhaps, may be because of the onerous provisions of Nigerian statutes on mortgages.¹²⁰ Section 126(2) PCL exonerates mortgagees from misdeeds committed while exercising the power of sale.

5.5 Purchasers without notice

The interest of the purchaser must be protected in exercising MPoS. However, the conditions for exercising the power must be present, namely: MPoS must have arisen and exerciseable. Fulfilling these conditions confers the title in the property in the purchaser.

A mortgagee who wants to validly transfer the title in the mortgaged land to the purchaser must have an unimpeachable title. This is because the mortgagee cannot give what he does not have. Having a valid title to land as a mortgagee entails having: (a) the Governor's consent; (b) necessary documents to confirm the title and (c) registration as the first registered owner of the land in the registration area under the Registration of Titles Law.¹²¹ A mortgagee with a valid title has a right to alienate the security provided that the power of sale is ripe for enforcement and all conditions for exercising it have been met.

A purchaser from the mortgagee is in a critical position because payment must have been made upon the completion of the sale contract while the mortgagor may refuse to give up possession through various legal tricks. The mortgagor may contend that MPoS is not ripe for the exercise and therefore applies to the court for annulment. In the suit, the mortgagee, the auctioneer and the purchaser may be joined as parties, or the purchaser who is not joined is left to protect his interest through an application to court as a co-defendant. Therefore, most mortgage deeds contain a "purchaser's protection clause" which immunizes the purchaser from the actions of the mortgagee even when the PoS has neither arisen nor exerciseable.¹²² In essence, a *bona fide* purchaser obtains a good title from the mortgagee while the mortgagor is bound with the contract, and his only remedy is damages against the mortgagee.¹²³

The purchaser is further protected by the statutes.¹²⁴ Section 126(2) of the PCL protects the interests of the purchaser by stating that the sale will not be invalidated by (a) the reason that the power of sale has not arisen or (b) that the power was not properly exercised; (c) or that notice was not given. All these infractions would not annul the sale but would attract damages to be paid by mortgagee.¹²⁵

¹¹⁹*Eka-Eteh v NHDS* (supra), See also *WAB Ltd v Savannah Bank Ventures Ltd* (2002) 10 NWLR (Pt. 775) 401

¹²⁰ See S. 20 CA 1881; S. 126 (2) PCL; S. 38 (2) MPL Lagos 2012

¹²¹ See Cap R4 Laws of Lagos State 2003; See also *Onashile v Idowu Ors*(1969) 1 All NLR (Pt 2) 313

¹²²Coote's *Law of Mortgages* 9th ed; vol.II at 925

¹²³ *Ibid*

¹²⁴ S S. 21 (2) CA; S.126 (2) PCL and S. 38(2) MPL

¹²⁵ *Ogudu v Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMB) Ltd* (1990) 6 NWLR (Pt 156) 330

In *Oguchi v FMB (Nig.) Ltd*,¹²⁶ the lower court explained that the statutory provision was for the protection of the purchasers and mortgagees who were acting *bona fide*. If the sale was conducted fraudulently the title could not pass to the purchaser. A purchaser may plead statutory protections if it can be proved to the court that: (1) the mortgagor mortgaged the property to the mortgagee-vendor; (2) the PoS has arisen because the mortgagor has defaulted; (3) the PoS was actually exercised by the mortgagee and, finally; (4) the purchaser, acquired the title in good faith.¹²⁷ The statutory protection is only available to the purchaser where the mortgagee has executed a deed of transfer. Since it protects the purchaser from the mortgagor's action commenced to defeat the title transferred. But the purchaser may not be able to benefit from statutory protection if the litigation commences to challenge the sale before the transfer.¹²⁸

Other remedies for the purchaser against the mortgagee were highlighted by Graham Paul J. in *Bada v Premier Thrift Society*.¹²⁹ First, the purchaser has a right to claim the mortgagee's right against the mortgagor. Also, the fraudulent mortgagor could be sued under the mortgage covenant. Finally, where the conveyance failed, the purchaser could still rely on the contract of sale to recoup the sum paid. The implication of this is that the purchaser is adequately protected under the law. The failure of the mortgagee to fulfill the promise of ensuring that all conditions necessary for the sale have been observed empowers the purchaser to seek damages or the refund of the amount already paid on the contract if it could no longer be achieved. This appears to be right to avoid fraud.

Remedies highlighted in the foregoing paragraphs could only be enjoyed by purchasers for value and without notice. A purchaser who has not furnished consideration for the sale or has the knowledge of the encumbrances on the security which makes the power of sale unripe is not entitled to them.

5.6 Proceeds of sale

The enforcement of the mortgage through sale has serious implications for all parties in the transaction. These include termination of mortgagor's redemptive right,¹³⁰ liability to pay damages for improper or fraudulent sale;¹³¹ and rendering account of the excess of proceeds.¹³²

A mortgagee is an agent for the surplus of the sale proceeds.¹³³ This trust is more apparent and clearly mandatory if multiple mortgages exist on the same property. This

¹²⁶ (1990) 6 NWLR (Pt. 156) 335.

¹²⁷ *Ibid*

¹²⁸ *Ogwuchi v FMB of Nigeria Ltd* (1990) 6 NWLR (Pt. 156), 330.

¹²⁹ (1936) 13 NLR 47.

¹³⁰ Ss. 111 and 112 PCL; S. 38 MPL 2012

¹³¹ S.21 CA 1881, 126 PCL 1959; 38(2) MPL 2012

¹³² S. 20 CA 1881; S. 127 PCL 1959; s. 39 MPL 2012

¹³³ *Governor of Kaduna State v Dada* (1986) S.C. 11; *LSPDC v Foreign Finance Corporation* (1987) 1 NWLR (Pt. 5) 413

indicates that the enforcement through sale could be embarked upon by any of the mortgagee but care must be taken that in the application of proceeds of sale, due process should be followed on the incumbrances on the property, in order of priority.

Mortgage statutes in Nigeria provide a guide for the disbursement of the proceeds when multiple mortgages exist.¹³⁴ Section 39, MPL provides for the excess to be used to offset prior encumbrances which are not excepted by the mortgage deed or the sale itself (if any). The section adds that the balance of the proceed sum shall be kept by the mortgagee (a) to offset all costs/charges and expenses incurred by the mortgagee, (b) to discharge the mortgage sum, interests and costs, and other money, if any, and or the mortgage; and (c) the balance shall be used to settle others who have interests in the mortgaged property. Hence, the proceeds of sale must be used to settle first, mortgages which have priority over their own. To find out such mortgagee(s), a search should be conducted at the registry in order not to be found negligent when the money is paid to the mortgagor.¹³⁵

When there is an excess of proceeds of sale, how is it handled? The excess proceeds must be handled in good faith.¹³⁶ Proceeds exceeding the outstanding mortgage sum, interest and cost of sale must be returned to the mortgagor.¹³⁷ The mortgagee must not waste or misuse the balance. As earlier mentioned, although the mortgagee is not a trustee of the power of sale, he is a trustee of the proceeds of sale.¹³⁸ Therefore, he must exercise caution so as not to squander the excess fund from the sale.

The statutory direction on the disbursement of proceeds of sale is to forestall fraud on the part of the mortgagee; ensure that previous encumbrances are taken care of and adequate protection must be taken on the interest of the mortgagor. Complying with these rules is a challenge that the lenders must surmount.

5.7 Abuse of court process

Nigerian courts are faced with actions, seeking to prevent the enforcement through power of sale. However, these have been variously abused by mortgagors in Nigeria who bring frivolous applications to prevent sale of the mortgaged property. The question is, under what circumstances can the courts grant interlocutory injunctions to stall the sale of the land? Courts have set some guidelines for granting this equitable remedy. First, the applicant must prove that the evidence which has been raised will stimulate a serious issue at the trial.¹³⁹ Also, he must adduce evidence that the common law remedy of damages canonised as Section 21(2) 1881, Section 126 (2) PCL 1959 and Section 38(2) MPL 2012 would not be adequate.¹⁴⁰ The proviso to these sections (which is similar across

¹³⁴ S. 21(3) CA 1881; S. 127 PCL 1959; S.39 MPL 2012

¹³⁵ *West London Commercial Bank v Reliance Permanent B.S* (1885) Ch. 190

¹³⁶ *Yorkshire Bank Plc v Hall* (1999) 1 W.L.R. 1713

¹³⁷ *Cuckmere Buck Co. Ltd v Mutual Finance Ltd* (1971) Ch 949

¹³⁸ *Banner v Berridge* (1881) 187 Ch.D 254

¹³⁹ *Obeya Memorial Hospital v Attorney General (Federation)* (1987) 3 NWLR (Pt 60) 325

¹⁴⁰ *Ibid*

jurisdictions) states categorically that a purchaser should be immune from defects in the sale, while the remedy of the mortgagor against the mortgagee is in damages. However, an interlocutory injunction may be deployed to prevent the sale and stop the loss. Furthermore, an injunction cannot be deployed to prevent an act that has been completed.¹⁴¹ Therefore, in appropriate situations where injustice would occur by the sale, the courts have granted injunction to protect the interest of the mortgagors.¹⁴²

In order to prevent frivolous applications, Nigerian courts have raised the bar by setting the rule that an applicant should prove beyond the level of probability that he possesses a legal right to be protected and that denying him the order will occasion irreparable damage.¹⁴³ Hence, the applicant should be able to undertake that if the case should go against him at the trial, he would be ready to remediate the mortgagee for any loss suffered.¹⁴⁴

Although the intention of equity in ensuring that injunctive reliefs were developed was to ensure justice was achieved for the weaker party in any contractual relationship, mortgage inclusive, their use to stall various proceedings in Nigerian courts have left much to be desired.

6. CONCLUSION

6.1 Summary

This study examined mortgagee's power of sale (MPoS) as a means of realising mortgages in Nigeria. It was noted that MPoS could be enforced based on the statutory provision or insertion of a clause in the agreement. The development of this enforcement method was traced through the common law to the Cranworth Act 1860 and finally to the Conveyancing Act, Section 19(1). The statutory provision of MPoS exists in other mortgage statutes¹⁴⁵ in Nigeria.

The judicial sale was also discussed as a sale that was done by the order of the courts. This mode of sale was found applicable to equitable mortgages of all shade except those by deed.¹⁴⁶ However, by the provision of s. 18(2) MPL, it appears that a depositor of mortgage deed accompanied by memorandum could enjoy MPoS as a legal mortgagee. However, the judicial sale was time could take a long period of time and the rules of High Court in Nigeria does not provide for it.

Furthermore, circumstances when the power could arise were discussed namely: when the mortgage was by deed; the payment was not made as scheduled and when no contrary intention was made to negate its exercise. Some exceptions and waivers to these

¹⁴¹*John Holt (Nig.) Ltd v John Holt African Wireless Union of Nig. & Cameroon* (1963) 1 All NLR 379

¹⁴²*Ibiyeye v Fojule* (2006) 3 NWLR (Pt 968) 640 SC.

¹⁴³*Obeya Memorial Hospital v Attorney General (Federation)* op. cit at 435, JSC See also *Abdullahi v Military Governor (Lagos)* (1989) 1 NWLR (Pt 97) 356

¹⁴⁴ Emeka Chianu, *Law of Securities for Advances Mortgage of Land*, 322

¹⁴⁵ S. 123 (1) PCL and S. 35(1) MPL

¹⁴⁶*Ibid*

rules were analysed. It was the requirement of the law that while the operation of the MPoS could be implied under the extant statutes, its exception should be specifically made because it could not be excluded from an agreement of mortgage by the fact that it was not provided for.

The mortgagee's duties to the mortgagor were examined to include exercise of good faith in the course of sale. This included the duty not to sell at gross undervalue, or in bad faith. It was however observed that the extant Nigerian laws did not provide for the duty of care by the mortgagee in exercising the MPoS. It was observed that the leading authorities in this area (*Medforth v Blake*¹⁴⁷ and Building Societies Act 1939¹⁴⁸) which insisted that price should be at best price are not applicable to MPOS in Nigeria, having come after 1st January, 1900.

The obligations of mortgagees to purchasers in MPoS were examined. These were observed to include: transfer of valid title; obtainment of requisite consents at customary law and the LUA and the availability of necessary documents. The purchasers were protected by the mortgage statutes.¹⁴⁹ However, the issue of priority of the purchasers and that of the purchasers without notice remain thorny.

In view of the above, the issue of allocating the proceeds of sale was discussed. It was noted that a mortgagee is not a trustee of the power of sale for the mortgagor. But he is accountable for the proceeds of sale. Mortgage statutes provided for the distribution of proceeds of sale to meet the position of equity and fairness and the priority of mortgages.¹⁵⁰ The laws gave specific directions on the distribution of the proceeds of sale.

6.2 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made statutes operating in various in Nigeria are: Many mortgage statutes operate in many parts of Nigeria, some with conflicting provisions with the Land Use Act 1978. Having been part of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria, any conflict between it and any mortgage statute renders such law void. Hence, various offensive parts of the Conveyancing Act 1881 and Property which contradict provisions of Land Use Act should be repealed and replaced with provisions that will be compliant with the right of occupancy regime of the Land Use Act 1978.

The enforcement of secured credit of the mortgagee through PoS is often frustrated by delays in obtaining Governor's consent under the LUA. To promote use of land for secured credit transactions in Nigeria and ensuring creditors can realise their credits when due, the onerous procedures of obtaining consent should be streamlined and made less cumbersome, through the amendments of sections 21 and 22 of LUA and setting uniform rules for obtaining consent throughout the Nigerian federation.

Also, the protection given to the purchase of mortgage sales without notice of the encumbrance is in order. However, statutory and judicial directions require strict

¹⁴⁷ Supra

¹⁴⁸ S. 10

¹⁴⁹ Ss. 21(2) CA; 126(2) PCL and 38(2) MPL

¹⁵⁰ Ss. 127(PCL) & s. 29 MPL

implementation to prevent fraud. Particularly, the rule that a mortgage sale to a third party without notice may only be invalidated, if only action is taken before the compilation of the transfer of title tracking of the mortgage deed may breed fraud, in a country where real estate frauds are prevalent. It is suggested that this position be amended to allow more time, perhaps a month after the mortgage deed.

Most land registries in Nigeria still operate manually. There is need to digitise them to ensure that adequate and updated records exist for land use, planning and management. This will reduce corruption in land matters and facilitate loan recovery.

The non-adoption of the uniform Model Mortgages and Foreclosures Law by most states of the Nigeria Federation is a major setback for the high penetration on mortgage market in Nigeria. It is recommended that to fast-track economic development, improve the deplorable statistics on housing in Nigeria, the law should be adopted, to streamline mortgage enforcement.